

A review of intelligent methods for condition monitoring and fault diagnosis of stator and rotor faults of induction machines

Omar Alshorman¹, Ahmad Alshorman²

¹Faculty of Engineering, and AlShrouk Trading Company, Najran University, Najran, Saudi Arabia

²Mechanical Engineering Department, Jordan University of Science and Technology, Irbid, Jordan

Article Info

Article history:

Received Sep 8, 2020

Revised Dec 5, 2020

Accepted Jan 15, 2021

Keywords:

Artificial intelligence

Condition monitoring

Fault detection and diagnosis

Induction motor

Rotor

Stator

ABSTRACT

Nowadays, induction motor (IM) is extensively used in industry, including mechanical and electrical applications. However, three main types of IM faults have been discussed in the literature, bearing, stator, and rotor. Importantly, stator and rotor (S/R) faults represent approximately 50%. Traditional condition monitoring (CM) and fault diagnosis (FD) methods require a high processing cost and much experience knowledge. To tackle this challenge, artificial intelligent (AI) based CM and FD techniques are extensively developed. However, there have been many review research papers for intelligent CM and FD machine learning methods of rolling elements bearings of IM in the literature. Whereas there is a lack in the literature, and there are not many review papers for both S/R intelligent CM and FD. Thus, the proposed study's main contribution is in reviewing the CM and FD of IM, especially for the stator and the rotor, based on AI methods. The paper also provides discussions on the main challenges and possible future works.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Omar Alshorman

Faculty of Engineering, and AlShrouk Trading Company

Najran University

Najran, Saudi Arabia

Email: omar2007_ahu@yahoo.com

1. INTRODUCTION

Recently, induction machines [1], such as induction motors (IM) [2, 3], are extensively used in several industrial processes and applications [4], including mining industries, chemical processes, gas and petroleum industries, transportation industries, compressor, and pumps [5, 6]. Importantly, IM has a vital and important use according to low price, reliability, robustness, and low maintenance cost [7, 8]. The performance and accuracy of IM can be impacted by three kinds of faults, such as electrical faults, mechanical faults, and environmental faults [9]. However, early and continuous condition monitoring (CM) and fault diagnosis (FD) of IM are crucial to increase availability, reliability, and safety, as well as reducing the risk of sudden accidents and failures [10, 11]. Recently, to follow up on the operating condition of IM and prevent faults and failures [12], CM and FD of IM have been developed by companies, scientists, researchers, and engineers [13-15]. However, several FD methodologies have been analyzed to achieve the best diagnostic results, including temperature analysis [16], vibration analysis [17], noise analysis [18], infrared analysis [19], current analysis [20], voltage analysis [21], electromagnetic field analysis [22], oil analysis [23], pressure analysis [24], ultrasound analysis [25], and also, sound and acoustic emission analysis [26].

Three main types of IM faults have been discussed in the literature, including bearing [27-29], stator [30, 31], and rotor [32-34] faults. Table 1 shows all types of faults of IM and their percentage [35]. However, bearing faults represent approximately 40%, while S/R faults represent approximately 50%. Figure 1 shows IM faults [36, 37].

Table 1. IM faults and their percentage

Fault type	Percentage
Stator	38%
Rotor	10%
Bearing	40%
Others	12%

Figure 1. Fault classification of IM

Recently, in the industrial internet of things (IIoT) [38, 39], big data [40-42], and recent information and communications technologies (ICTs) [43] era, many CM and FD methods are based on different techniques are employed. That includes the internet of things [44], machine and deep learnings [45], advanced signal and image processing for time, frequency, and time-frequency domains [46, 47], and expert systems [48]. In recent literature, there have been many review papers for intelligence CM and FD machine learning methods of rolling elements bearings of IM [49, 50]. However, there is a lack in the literature and there are not many review papers for both S/R intelligent CM and FD. The S/R CM and FD framework are shown in Figure 2. This study aims to propose a systematic literature review for CM and FD of the IM, especially for S/R based on artificial intelligent (AI) methods shown in Figure 3. The study also points out the advantages and drawbacks of each method. Finally, challenges and possible future trends are also addressed.

Figure 2. S/R CM and FD framework

Figure 3. Types of AI methods in CM and FD [51, 52]

2. RELATED WORKS

2.1. Stator faults (SFs) diagnosis

Stator faults are considered to be one of the most faults of the IM [53, 54]. Consequently, in [55], the feature extraction method applied to the thermal images is used to diagnose SFs of the IM. This method is depended on the states of the selected area. The primary use of AI algorithms in this study is in the classification stage. Notably, two types of classifiers, the nearest neighbor (NN) and the Gaussian mixture models (GMM) achieved the obtained feature vectors' classification stage. As a result, the effectiveness of AI recognition and classification algorithms used in this study research was very high. In [56], a neuro-fuzzy classifier for boundary detection is used to diagnose IM's SF using line current vector obtained from stator current. Moreover, this simple method is applied as an FD of rotor faults based on the image's obtained pattern. In [57], a stator-winding-fault prediction approach of IM using fuzzy optimization and multi-scale entropy is introduced.

Furthermore, vibration signals along with the motor's current signature are utilized to diagnose the SFs under different operating speeds. The wavelet transform technique is applied in order to removing noise. Notably, neuro-fuzzy is applied to model and predict the SFs. As a result, the grey-fuzzy investigation showed the effectiveness in the on-line predicting of the stator winding faults. In [58], a short circuit stator-fault analysis approach of IM using information measures and ANN is introduced.

Moreover, feature vectors are measured as a mutual information technique. Importantly, two ANN topologies are used in this proposed approach. Multilayer perceptron (MLP) along with radial basis function (RBF) are applied as pattern recognition and classification processes. As a result, the error margin of the MLP networks is less than the margin of the RBF. However, the MLP is considered as the best ANN topology where experimental accuracy is 99%. According to [59], the FD approach based on AI is presented using both vibration and stator current analyses. Discrete wavelet transform (DWT) and matching pursuit are applied in the feature extraction stage. Following that, five classifiers are applied: subspace, fine and weighted nearest neighbor (NN), bagged trees, and support vector machine (SVM). As a result, the proposed study shows high classification accuracy (around 100%). In [60], a stator inter-turn FD tool based

on ANN is presented. Moreover, the tool is developed under several fault sizes and loads. A steady-state electromechanical torque signature in time and frequency domains is applied as feature extraction method. As a classification method, a neural network is employed. As a result, 88-96% classification accuracy is obtained in this research study. Table 2 summarizes AI studies of CM and FD SFs.

Table 2. AI studies of CM and FD for SFs

Reference	Analysis type	Feature extraction	Classification	Highlights
[55]	Thermal images	Method of Area Selection of States	NN and GMM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reliable diagnostic method - The efficiency of the proposed method is 100 % - Diagnosing multiple states and faults - Several types of motors (DC, IM, and synchronous) could be benefited using this method
[56]	Current analysis	Image processing-based pattern recognition method	Neuro-fuzzy classifier	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Current vector image pattern-based automatic technique is proposed - No expert is needed - The average recognition rate was 99%
[57]	Current and vibration analyses	Multi-scale entropy (MSE) algorithm	Grey fuzzy classifier	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SF prediction technique is presented - Diagnose the SFs under different operating speeds - Fuzzy logic along with grey relational analysis (GRA) and are applied - The proposed method can be used as on-line monitoring to reduce the risk of SFs - The multi-performance index (GFRG) is 0.6 for faulty stator
[58]	Current analysis	Pattern recognition based mutual information method	Artificial neural networks (ANN)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The method to detect stator short circuit method is presented - Several load levels and power supply voltage unbalance-based method - The classification accuracy is 99%
[59]	Current and vibration analyses	Matching pursuit, and discrete wavelet transform (DWT)	SVM, KNN, and bagging	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Two types of analyses (current and vibration) - Several electrical and mechanical faults are analyzed - The classification accuracy is 99%
[60]	Current analysis	Steady-state electromechanical torque signature	NN	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - On-line detection method for stator inter-turn faults is proposed - Fault severity estimation are applied - 88-96% classification accuracy is obtained
[61]	External magnetic field	DWT		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Energy evaluation-based FD technique is proposed - The transient state and the severity of the fault are analyzed - The energy level is increased (89.19%) at start-up state
[62]	Current analysis	Fourier transform (FFT) along with DWT		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - FD based on FFT and DWT is presented to diagnose inter-turn short circuit faults. - DWT is applied to deal with frequency spectrum for different load and speed - The proposed method cannot show a clear indication of fault severity.
[63]	Current analysis	Optimal wavelet tree and predator search genetic algorithm (PSGA)	Backpropagation NN	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stator winding inter-turn short circuit FD technique is proposed - Improving the speed and precision of network training is occurred - Diagnosing multiple rotor faults - accurate results are achieved compared with the wavelet package method

2.2. Rotor faults (RFs) diagnosis

Open and broken bar rotor FD of the IM is vital [64, 65]. In [66], intelligent FD of broken rotor bar for IM using acoustic signals analysis is introduced. Two feature extraction methods are applied. The first one is based on frequency selection, and the second one is called SMOFS-32-MULTIEXPANDED-1-GROUP. KNN, backpropagation NN, and a modified classifier called word's coding are trained and applied in the classification stage.. High classification accuracy for real data is the main advantage of the proposed method. However, the backpropagation NN showed the best results as a classifier in this research study. In [67],

AI experimental comparative evaluation FD study under various operating conditions using current signals is proposed.

Moreover, a feature-based method for automatic rotor FD of IM is developed. As feature extraction and selection stages, statistical measures on the signal's time and frequency domains are applied. Importantly, six machine-learning techniques are used in this study, naive Bayes, KNN, bootstrap aggregating (bagging), boosting algorithms (AdaBoost), multilayer perceptron (MLP) neural network, and SVM. However, KNN showed the worst results than the other classifiers just before MLP and SVM, whereas naive Bayes and bagging classifiers showed the best results. In [68], an on-line method for FD of broken rotor bars (BRP) using vibration analysis based on entropy is proposed.

Furthermore, the proposed method could deal with several operations. The Shannon entropy is applied to seek diagnostic vibration data. Significantly, the *K*-means cluster algorithm is employed. Importantly, as a result, in this study, *K*-means cluster-based Shannon entropy showed the ability to detect four severities of rotor damage, which include HLT condition, HBRB, 1BRB, and 2BRB. In [69], an early FD approach of the rotor based on empirical mode decomposition (EMD), ANN, and wavelet transform (WT) using vibration signals is proposed. WT is applied to decompose vibration signals into several bandwidths; then, EMD is applied to obtain corresponding frequency bandwidth from intrinsic mode functions (IMFs). Notably, in the classification stage, three layers back propagation neural network model is employed. However, the comprehensive approach of WPD, EMD and BPNN showed good diagnosis, extraction, and classification results less power signal. In [70], a data fusion technique for the rotor based on information entropy and NN using vibration signals is introduced. By applying the information entropy method, three characteristics could extract, namely, power spectrum, singular spectrum, and approximate entropies. A feature fusion model based on Probabilistic (PNN) is developed as an FD and classification. However, PNN based information entropy classifier showed significantly higher accuracy. In [71], a CM and FD approach for crack mentoring in the rotor using vibration signals is proposed.

Moreover, in this approach, WT and ANN are applied. The WT is applied as a feature extraction process. As a result, this method shows good diagnosis results. Furthermore, the signal-to-noise ratio increases as a result of speed's increasing; thus, the fault would be obvious. According to [72], a diagnostic approach for several loads based on the pseudo method and current signal is proposed. The pseudo-spectrum method is developed to diagnose fault frequency components. However, detecting fault at light load conditions is the main advantage of this method. Table 3 (see in Appendix) summarizes AI studies of CM and FD of RFs. Table 4 (see in Appendix) summarizes AI algorithms used for CM and FD for the rotor and the IM's stator.

3 CHALLENGES AND FUTURE TRENDS

Finding an intelligent CM and FD method for the rotor and IM's stator is considered a challenging task [76-78]. This section summarizes the challenges and future trends facing CM and FD of IM's stator and rotor.

- It is crucial to develop cost-effective, fast, non-invasive, non-intrusiveness, wireless, energy-efficient, and highly accurate sensors to solve conventional sensors problems [36].
- AI algorithms have to be used to build a better performance, low cost, continuous, and on-line CM and FD method [79].
- AI hybrid systems should be developed to deal with multiple faults [80].
- AI system that can diagnose all IM faults (bearing, stator, and rotor) should be developed [81].
- Fault's size and severity based on AI techniques should be discussed more [82].
- Prognostic techniques should be developed based on AI [83].
- Big data analytics, expert systems, advanced signal processing algorithms, and data fusion should be used along with AI to develop CM and FD algorithms [84-86].
- Fuzzy-based fault-tolerant and internet of things (IoT) techniques based on advanced sensors technology should be developed [87-91].

4. CONCLUSION

Reducing maintenance costs and improving the availability and reliability of machines are crucial in the modern industrial world. CM and FD are being used to monitor the health of machines. Thus, the article presents a brief review of AI methods for CM and FD of S/R faults of induction machines such as IM. S/R faults represent approximately 50% of IM's total faults. However, developing non-invasive, early, continuous, and accurate fault diagnostic techniques based on AI methods is challenging. Thus, the proposed study discussed the literature methods and highlighted the advantages and disadvantages of each method.

APPENDIX

Table 3. AI studies of CM and FD for RFs

Reference	Analysis type	Feature extraction	Classification	Highlights
[66]	Acoustic signals	Frequencies Selection Multiexpand technique	BPNN, and words coding classifiers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Intelligent FD technique based acoustic signals is proposed - Diagnosing multiple RFs - The proposed technique is inexpensive, instantly measurable, and non-invasive - 88.19-100% classification accuracy is achieved
[67]	Current analysis	Time and frequency domain analyses	KNN, NN, SVM, Naive Bayes, and Bagging	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Diagnosing multiple RFs - Four different power supplies and loaded are applied - Naive Bayes and Bagging (AUC=0.798, 0.900) achieved the best accuracy, and k-NN is the worst classifier.
[68]	Vibration signal	Shannon entropy	K- means cluster algorithm	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - An on-line, low cost and simple monitoring method is proposed - The proposed method is implemented using FPGA - Start-up transient and three severities of damage are proposed - Low consumption of FPGA (11.67%) is achieved - The effectiveness of the proposed study is 100%
[69]	Vibration signal	WPD and EMD	BPNN	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - An early fault diagnosis approach with a fault identification model is proposed - Diagnosing multiple RFs - The diagnosis result satisfies the actual condition.
[70]	Vibration signal	Information entropy	Probabilistic NN	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The fusion model for fault diagnosis approach is presented - Entropies (approximate, power spectrum, and singular spectrum) are obtained in the feature extraction stage - 80–95% classification accuracy is achieved
[71]	Vibration signal	WPT	ANN	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - An automatic CM and FD approach based on the Wavelet packet technique for a cracked rotor is proposed - Severity level estimation is applied - High performance and low computational cost are the main advantages of this method
[72]	Current analysis	Pseudo-spectrum method	Multiple signal classification (MUSIC)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Half broken rotor bar diagnostic approach is presented - Various load conditions are applied - light load condition fault capabilities - The proposed method shows effectiveness than motor current signature analysis (MCSA), especially for light load condition
[73]	Current analysis	Continuous transforms	-	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Start-up current analyzing based reliable detection FD method is presented - The proposed method improved visualization of the fault components - Better diagnostic results compared with discrete transforms are achieved - Tracking a larger number of fault harmonics is applied, and false alarms are obtained
[74]	Current analysis	Simulated Annealing algorithm and an ensemble composed of multivariate decision trees	KNN, random forest, and regression trees	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - FD method with feature selection process and classification is proposed - Computational requirements of the diagnosis tool are decreased - The accuracy of the proposed study is approximately 100%
[75]	Electromagnetic torque monitoring	Finite element method	-	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The magnetic flux density is analyzed with a frequency range of 300 Hz - Different design variables are applied - Compared with traditional low-frequency torque signature methods, electromagnetic torque monitoring approach show best results

Table 4. AI studies for CM and FD for the rotor and the stator of IM

The method	Advantages	Drawbacks
SVM	Good performance and good classification accuracy	Efficient only with a small set of data
KNN	Simple	Low performance and classification accuracy
Random forest	Good classification accuracy	Over-fitting
Decision tree	High-dimensionality	More computational time is required
Regression	Simple and deal with small data	Low performance and classification accuracy
Bagging	Deal with big data	More computational time is required.
K- means clustering	Good performance and classification accuracy	Difficult to implement
Naive Bayes	Deal with big data	Low classification accuracy
Neuro-Fuzzy	Deal with big data and good diagnosis accuracy	More computational time is required.
ANN	Deal with big data, good performance, and good diagnosis accuracy	More training and computational time is required.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. Puche-Panadero, J. Martinez-Roman, A. Sapena-Bano, J. Burriel-Valencia, and M. Riera-Guasp, "Fault Diagnosis in the Slip-Frequency Plane of Induction Machines Working in Time-Varying Conditions," *Sensors*, vol. 20, no. 12, 2020, Art. no. 3398.
- [2] X. Tang, L. Zhuang, J. Cai, and C. Li, "Multi-fault classification based on support vector machine trained by chaos particle swarm optimization," *Knowledge-Based Systems*, vol. 23, no. 5, pp. 486-490, 2010.
- [3] A. Singh, B. Grant, R. DeFour, C. Sharma, and S. Bahadoorsingh, "A review of induction motor fault modeling," *Electric Power Systems Research*, vol. 133, pp. 191-197, 2016.
- [4] N. G. Ozelik, U. E. Dogru, M. Imeryuz, and L. T. Ergene, "Synchronous reluctance motor vs. Induction motor at low-power industrial applications: Design and comparison," *Energies*, vol. 12, no. 11, pp. 2190-2210, 2019.
- [5] A. Valderrabano-Gonzalez, J. C. Rosas-Caro, F. Beltran-Carbajal, I. Lopez-Garcia, R. Tapia-Olvera, and H. A. Gabbar, "Large induction motor drive performance comparison," *2018 IEEE International Autumn Meeting on Power, Electronics and Computing (ROPEC)*, Ixtapa, Mexico, 2018, pp. 1-6.
- [6] R. Gayathri and S. K. Vasudevan, "Internet of things based smart health monitoring of industrial standard motors," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Informatics (IJEI)*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 361-367, 2018.
- [7] K. Kim and A. G. Parlos, "Induction motor fault diagnosis based on neuropredictors and wavelet signal processing," *IEEE/ASME Transactions on Mechatronics*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 201-219, 2002.
- [8] M. Korzonek, G. Tarchala, and T. Orłowska-Kowalska, "A review on MRAS-type speed estimators for reliable and efficient induction motor drives," *ISA transactions*, vol. 93, pp. 1-13, 2019.
- [9] S. Karmakar, S. Chattopadhyay, M. Mitra, and S. Sengupta, "Induction motor fault diagnosis," *Springer Link*, vol. 25, 2016.
- [10] C. Lu, Y. Wang, M. Ragulskis, and Y. Cheng, "Fault diagnosis for rotating machinery: A method based on image processing," *PLoS one*, vol. 11, no. 10, 2016, Art. no. e0164111.
- [11] J. Pons-Llinares, J. A. Antonino-Daviu, M. Riera-Guasp, S. B. Lee, T.-j. Kang, and C. Yang, "Advanced induction motor rotor fault diagnosis via continuous and discrete time-frequency tools," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 62, no. 3, pp. 1791-1802, 2014.
- [12] S. L. Souad, B. Azzedine, and S. Meradi, "Fault diagnosis of rolling element bearings using artificial neural network," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 5288-5295, 2020.
- [13] A. Glowacz, W. Glowacz, Z. Glowacz, and J. Kozik, "Early fault diagnosis of bearing and stator faults of the single-phase induction motor using acoustic signals," *Measurement*, vol. 113, pp. 1-9, 2018.
- [14] O. AlShorman, M. Masadeh, F. Alkahtani and A. AlShorman, "A Review of Condition Monitoring and Fault Diagnosis and Detection of Rotating Machinery Based on Image Aspects," *2020 International Conference on Data Analytics for Business and Industry: Way Towards a Sustainable Economy (ICDABI)*, Sakheer, Bahrain, 2020, pp. 1-5, doi: 10.1109/ICDABI51230.2020.9325635.
- [15] H. -C. Chang, Y. -M. Jheng, C. -C. Kuo, and Y. -M. Hsueh, "Induction motors condition monitoring system with fault diagnosis using a hybrid approach," *Energies*, vol. 12, no. 8, pp. 1471-1483, 2019.
- [16] D. Wang, Y. Liang, C. Li, P. Yang, C. Zhou, and L. Gao, "Thermal equivalent network method for calculating stator temperature of a shielding induction motor," *International Journal of Thermal Sciences*, vol. 147, p. 106149, 2020.
- [17] R. Misra, K. Shinghal, A. Saxena, and A. Agarwal, "Industrial Motor Bearing Fault Detection Using Vibration Analysis," in *International Conference on Intelligent Computing and Smart Communication 2019*, 2020, pp. 827-839.
- [18] S. Sathyan, U. Aydin, and A. Belahcen, "Acoustic noise computation of electrical motors using the boundary element method," *Energies*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 245-258, 2020.
- [19] F. Jeffali, A. Ouariach, B. El Kihel, and A. Nougouai, "Diagnosis of three-phase induction motor and the impact on the kinematic chain using non-destructive technique of infrared thermography," *Infrared Physics & Technology*, vol. 102, 2019, Art. no. 102970.
- [20] X. Chen and Z. Feng, "Induction motor stator current analysis for planetary gearbox fault diagnosis under time-varying speed conditions," *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing*, vol. 140, 2020, Art. no. 106691.
- [21] P. Gnaciński, D. Hallmann, M. Pepliński, and P. Jankowski, "The effects of voltage subharmonics on cage induction machine," *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, vol. 111, pp. 125-131, 2019.

- [22] A. Yuejun, Z. Zhiheng, L. Ming, W. Guangyu, K. Xiangling, and L. Zaihang, "Influence of asymmetrical stator axes on the electromagnetic field and driving characteristics of canned induction motor," *IET Electric Power Applications*, vol. 13, no. 8, pp. 1229-1239, 2019.
- [23] T. Ding, N. Takorabet, F. -M. Sargos, and X. Wang, "Design and analysis of different line-start PM synchronous motors for oil-pump applications," *IEEE Transactions on Magnetics*, vol. 45, no. 3, pp. 1816-1819, 2009.
- [24] G. Despret, M. Hecquet, V. Lanfranchi, and M. Fakam, "Skew effect on the radial pressure of induction motor," *2016 Eleventh International Conference on Ecological Vehicles and Renewable Energies (EVER)*, Monte Carlo, Monaco, 2016, pp. 1-6.
- [25] B. C. Gibson *et al.*, "Increased excitability induced in the primary motor cortex by transcranial ultrasound stimulation," *Frontiers in neurology*, vol. 9, 2018, Art. no. 1007.
- [26] P. A. Delgado-Arredondo, D. Morinigo-Sotelo, R. A. Osornio-Rios, J. G. Avina-Cervantes, H. Rostro-Gonzalez, and R. de Jesus Romero-Troncoso, "Methodology for fault detection in induction motors via sound and vibration signals," *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing*, vol. 83, pp. 568-589, 2017.
- [27] Z. Wu, H. Jiang, K. Zhao, and X. Li, "An adaptive deep transfer learning method for bearing fault diagnosis," *Measurement*, vol. 151, 2020, Art. no. 107227.
- [28] Z. Chen, A. Mauricio, W. Li, and K. Gryllias, "A deep learning method for bearing fault diagnosis based on Cyclic Spectral Coherence and Convolutional Neural Networks," *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing*, vol. 140, p. 106683, 2020.
- [29] J. Wang, Y. Liang, Y. Zheng, R. X. Gao, and F. Zhang, "An integrated fault diagnosis and prognosis approach for predictive maintenance of wind turbine bearing with limited samples," *Renewable Energy*, vol. 145, pp. 642-650, 2020.
- [30] T. A. Shifat and J. W. Hur, "An Effective Stator Fault Diagnosis Framework of BLDC Motor Based on Vibration and Current Signals," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 106968-106981, 2020.
- [31] K. N. Gytakis and A. J. M. Cardoso, "Reliable Detection of Stator Inter-Turn Faults of Very Low Severity Level in Induction Motors," *IECON 2019 - 45th Annual Conference of the IEEE Industrial Electronics Society*, Lisbon, Portugal, 2019, pp. 1290-1295.
- [32] H. Deng, Y. Diao, W. Wu, J. Zhang, M. Ma, and X. Zhong, "A high-speed D-CART on-line fault diagnosis algorithm for rotor systems," *Applied Intelligence*, vol. 50, pp. 29-41, 2020.
- [33] M. Xia, G. Han, Y. Zhang, and J. Wan, "Intelligent fault diagnosis of rotor-bearing system under varying working conditions with modified transfer CNN and thermal images," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, 2020.
- [34] P. Jadhav, S. G. Kumbhar, R. Desavale, and S. B. Patil, "Distributed Fault Diagnosis of Rotor-Bearing System using Dimensional Analysis and Experimental Methods," *Measurement*, vol. 166, 2020, Art. no. 108239.
- [35] K. S. Gaeid and H. W. Ping, "Wavelet fault diagnosis and tolerant of induction motor: A review," *International Journal of Physical Sciences*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 358-376, 2011.
- [36] A. Choudhary, D. Goyal, S. L. Shimi, and A. Akula, "Condition monitoring and fault diagnosis of induction motors: A review," *Archives of Computational Methods in Engineering*, vol. 26, pp. 1221-1238, 2019.
- [37] P. Gangsar and R. Tiwari, "Signal based condition monitoring techniques for fault detection and diagnosis of induction motors: A state-of-the-art review," *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing*, vol. 144, 2020, Art. no. 106908.
- [38] W. Z. Khan, M. Rehman, H. M. Zangoti, M. K. Afzal, N. Armi, and K. Salah, "Industrial internet of things: Recent advances, enabling technologies and open challenges," *Computers & Electrical Engineering*, vol. 81, 2020, Art. no. 106522.
- [39] H. Boyes, B. Hallaq, J. Cunningham, and T. Watson, "The industrial internet of things (IIoT): An analysis framework," *Computers in industry*, vol. 101, pp. 1-12, 2018.
- [40] J. Wu, S. Guo, J. Li, and D. Zeng, "Big data meet green challenges: Big data toward green applications," *IEEE Systems Journal*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 888-900, 2016.
- [41] J. Wu, S. Guo, J. Li, and D. Zeng, "Big data meet green challenges: Greening big data," *IEEE Systems Journal*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 873-887, 2016.
- [42] R. Atat, L. Liu, J. Wu, G. Li, C. Ye, and Y. Yang, "Big data meet cyber-physical systems: A panoramic survey," *IEEE Access*, vol. 6, pp. 73603-73636, 2018.
- [43] J. Wu, S. Guo, H. Huang, W. Liu, and Y. Xiang, "Information and communications technologies for sustainable development goals: state-of-the-art, needs and perspectives," *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 2389-2406, 2018.
- [44] C. Kan, H. Yang, and S. Kumara, "Parallel computing and network analytics for fast Industrial Internet-of-Things (IIoT) machine information processing and condition monitoring," *Journal of manufacturing systems*, vol. 46, pp. 282-293, 2018.
- [45] M. Rungruanukul and T. Siriborvornratanakul, "Deep Learning Based Gesture Classification for Hand Physical Therapy Interactive Program," in *International Conference on Human-Computer Interaction*, vol. 12198, pp. 349-358, 2020.
- [46] J. Faiz, A. Takbani, and E. Mazaheri-Tehrani, "A Review of Application of Signal Processing Techniques for Fault Diagnosis of Induction Motors-Part I," *AUT Journal of Electrical Engineering*, vol. 49, no. 2, pp. 109-122, 2017.
- [47] C. Kerdvibulvech, "Hybrid model of human hand motion for cybernetics application," *2014 IEEE International Conference on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics (SMC)*, San Diego, CA, USA, 2014, pp. 2367-2372.
- [48] M. Žarković and Z. Stojković, "Analysis of artificial intelligence expert systems for power transformer condition monitoring and diagnostics," *Electric Power Systems Research*, vol. 149, pp. 125-136, 2017.
- [49] C. Malla and I. Panigrahi, "Review of condition monitoring of rolling element bearing using vibration analysis and other techniques," *Journal of Vibration Engineering & Technologies*, vol. 7, pp. 407-414, 2019.

- [50] A. Kumar and R. Kumar, "Role of signal processing, modeling and decision making in the diagnosis of rolling element bearing defect: a review," *Journal of Nondestructive Evaluation*, vol. 38, no. 5, 2019.
- [51] P. Kumar and A. S. Hati, "Review on Machine Learning Algorithm Based Fault Detection in Induction Motors," *Archives of Computational Methods in Engineering*, pp. 1-12, 2020.
- [52] Y. Lei, B. Yang, X. Jiang, F. Jia, N. Li, and A. K. Nandi, "Applications of machine learning to machine fault diagnosis: A review and roadmap," *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing*, vol. 138, 2020, Art. no. 106587.
- [53] G. Mirzaeva, K. I. Saad, and M. G. Jahromi, "Comprehensive Diagnostics of Induction Motor Faults Based on Measurement of Space and Time Dependencies of Air Gap Flux," *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, vol. 53, no. 3, pp. 2657-2666, 2017.
- [54] C. D. Tran, P. Brandstetter, M. C. H. Nguyen, S. D. Ho, H. D. Bach, and P. N. Pham, "A robust diagnosis method for speed sensor fault based on stator currents in the RFOC induction motor drive," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 3035-3046, 2020.
- [55] A. Glowacz and Z. Glowacz, "Diagnostics of stator faults of the single-phase induction motor using thermal images," MoASoS and selected classifiers, *Measurement*, vol. 93, pp. 86-93, 2016.
- [56] T. Amaral, V. Pires, J. Martins, A. Pires, and M. Crisostomo, "Image processing to a neuro-fuzzy classifier for detection and diagnosis of induction motor stator fault," *IECON 2007-33rd Annual Conference of the IEEE Industrial Electronics Society*, Taipei, Taiwan, 2007, pp. 2408-2413.
- [57] A. Verma, S. Sarangi, and M. H. Kolekar, "Stator winding fault prediction of induction motors using multi-scale entropy and grey fuzzy optimization methods," *Computers & Electrical Engineering*, vol. 40, no. 7, pp. 2246-2258, 2014.
- [58] G. H. Bazan, P. R. Scalassara, W. Endo, A. Goedel, W. F. Godoy, and R. H. C. Palácios, "Stator fault analysis of three-phase induction motors using information measures and artificial neural networks," *Electric Power Systems Research*, vol. 143, pp. 347-356, 2017.
- [59] M. Z. Ali, M. N. S. K. Shabbir, X. Liang, Y. Zhang, and T. Hu, "Machine learning-based fault diagnosis for single- and multi-faults in induction motors using measured stator currents and vibration signals," *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, vol. 55, no. 3, pp. 2378-2391, 2019.
- [60] L. Maraaba, Z. Al-Hamouz, and M. Abido, "An efficient stator inter-turn fault diagnosis tool for induction motors," *Energies*, vol. 11, no. 3, 2018, Art. no. 653.
- [61] H. Cherif, A. Menacer, R. Romary, and R. Pusca, "Dispersion field analysis using discrete wavelet transform for inter-turn stator fault detection in induction motors," *2017 IEEE 11th International Symposium on Diagnostics for Electrical Machines, Power Electronics and Drives (SDEMPED)*, Tinos, 2017, pp. 104-109.
- [62] R. Kechida, A. Menacer, H. Talhaoui, and H. Cherif, "Discrete wavelet transform for stator fault detection in induction motors," *2015 IEEE 10th International Symposium on Diagnostics for Electrical Machines, Power Electronics and Drives (SDEMPED)*, Guarda, Portugal, 2015, pp. 104-109.
- [63] S. Liping, T. Jiasheng, W. Panpan, H. Li, and Z. Xiaolei, "Stator fault diagnosis of induction motors using the optimal wavelet tree and improved BP neural network," *Transactions of China Electrotechnical Society*, vol. 30, no. 24, pp. 38-45, 2015.
- [64] M. Sabouri, M. Ojaghi, J. Faiz, and A. J. M. Cardoso, "Model-based unified technique for identifying severities of stator inter-turn and rotor broken bar faults in SCIMs," *IET Electric Power Applications*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 204-211, 2020.
- [65] P. Luong and W. Wang, "Smart Sensor-based Synergistic Analysis for Rotor Bar Fault Detection of Induction Motors," *IEEE/ASME Transactions on Mechatronics*, vol. 25, no. 2, pp. 1067-1075, 2020.
- [66] A. Glowacz, "Acoustic based fault diagnosis of three-phase induction motor," *Applied Acoustics*, vol. 137, pp. 82-89, 2018.
- [67] I. Martin-Diaz, D. Morinigo-Sotelo, O. Duque-Perez, and R. J. Romero-Troncoso, "An Experimental Comparative Evaluation of Machine Learning Techniques for Motor Fault Diagnosis Under Various Operating Conditions," *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, vol. 54, no. 3, pp. 2215-2224, 2018.
- [68] D. Camarena-Martinez, M. Valtierra-Rodriguez, J. P. Amezquita-Sanchez, D. Granados-Lieberman, R. J. Romero-Troncoso, and A. Garcia-Perez, "Shannon Entropy and K-Means Method for Automatic Diagnosis of Broken Rotor Bars in Induction Motors Using Vibration Signals," *Shock and Vibration*, vol. 2016, pp. 1-10, 2016.
- [69] G. F. Bin, J. J. Gao, X. J. Li, and B. S. Dhillon, "Early fault diagnosis of rotating machinery based on wavelet packets-Empirical mode decomposition feature extraction and neural network," *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing*, vol. 27, pp. 696-711, 2012.
- [70] Q. Jiang, Y. Shen, H. Li, and F. Xu, "New Fault Recognition Method for Rotary Machinery Based on Information Entropy and a Probabilistic Neural Network," *Sensors (Basel)*, vol. 18, no. 2, Art. no. 337, 2018.
- [71] M. J. Gómez, C. Castejón, and J. C. García-Prada, "Automatic condition monitoring system for crack detection in rotating machinery," *Reliability Engineering & System Safety*, vol. 152, pp. 239-247, 2016.
- [72] G. Singh and V. Naikan, "Detection of half broken rotor bar fault in VFD driven induction motor drive using motor square current MUSIC analysis," *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing*, vol. 110, pp. 333-348, 2018.
- [73] J. A. Antonino-Daviu, J. Pons-Llinares, and S. B. Lee, "Advanced rotor fault diagnosis for medium-voltage induction motors via continuous transforms," *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, vol. 52, no. 5, pp. 4503-4509, 2016.
- [74] I. Martin-Diaz, D. Morinigo-Sotelo, O. Duque-Perez, R. A. Osornio-Rios, and R. J. Romero-Troncoso, "Hybrid algorithmic approach oriented to incipient rotor fault diagnosis on induction motors," *ISA transactions*, vol. 80, pp. 427-438, 2018.

- [75] K. N. Gyftakis, D. V. Spyropoulos, J. C. Kappatou, and E. D. Mitronikas, "A novel approach for broken bar fault diagnosis in induction motors through torque monitoring," *IEEE Transactions on Energy Conversion*, vol. 28, no. 2, pp. 267-277, 2013.
- [76] P. Fu, J. Wang, X. Zhang, L. Zhang, and R. X. Gao, "Dynamic Routing-based Multimodal Neural Network for Multi-sensory Fault Diagnosis of Induction Motor," *Journal of Manufacturing Systems*, vol. 55, pp. 264-272, 2020.
- [77] F. B. Abid, M. Sallem, and A. Braham, "Robust Interpretable Deep Learning for Intelligent Fault Diagnosis of Induction Motors," *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 69, no. 6, pp. 3506-3515, 2019.
- [78] M. Rani, S. Dhok, and R. Deshmukh, "A Machine Condition Monitoring Framework Using Compressed Signal Processing," *Sensors*, vol. 20, no. 1, 2020, Art. no. 319.
- [79] R. Liu, B. Yang, E. Zio, and X. Chen, "Artificial intelligence for fault diagnosis of rotating machinery: A review," *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing*, vol. 108, pp. 33-47, 2018.
- [80] N. Rajeswaran, M. L. Swarupa, T. S. Rao, and K. Chetaswi, "Hybrid artificial intelligence based fault diagnosis of svpwm voltage source inverters for induction motor," *Materials Today: Proceedings*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 565-571, 2018.
- [81] Y. Liu and A. M. Bazzi, "A review and comparison of fault detection and diagnosis methods for squirrel-cage induction motors: State of the art," *ISA transactions*, vol. 70, pp. 400-409, 2017.
- [82] N. R. Devi, D. S. Sarma, and P. R. Rao, "Diagnosis and classification of stator winding insulation faults on a three-phase induction motor using wavelet and MNN," *IEEE Transactions on Dielectrics and Electrical Insulation*, vol. 23, no. 5, pp. 2543-2555, 2016.
- [83] S. Kumar, D. Mukherjee, P. K. Guchhait, R. Banerjee, A. K. Srivastava, D. Vishwakarma *et al.*, "A comprehensive review of condition based prognostic maintenance (CBPM) for induction motor," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 90690-90704, 2019.
- [84] J. Si, Y. Li, and S. Ma, "Intelligent fault diagnosis for industrial big data," *Journal of signal processing systems*, vol. 90, no. 1, pp. 1221-1233, 2018.
- [85] O. M. Al-Shorman, "Lossy Digital Image Compression Technique Using Run-Length Encoding and Frei-Chen Basis," Yarmouk University, 2012.
- [86] M. Al-khassaweneh and O. AlShorman, "Frei-Chen bases based lossy digital image compression technique," *Applied Computing and Informatics*, 2020.
- [87] Alshorman, A. M., Alshorman, O., Irfan, M., Glowacz, A., Muhammad, F., Caesarendra, W., "Fuzzy-Based Fault-Tolerant Control for Omnidirectional Mobile Robot," *Machines*, vol. 8, no. 3, 2020, Art. no. 55.
- [88] O. AlShorman, B. AlShorman, M. Alkhassaweneh, F. Alkahtani, "A Review of Internet of Medical Things (IoMT) -Based Remote Health Monitoring through Wearable Sensors: A Case Study for Diabetic Patients," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science (IJECS)*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 414-422, 2020.
- [89] O. AlShorman, B. Alshorman, F. Alkahtani, "A review of wearable sensors-based monitoring with daily physical activity to manage type 2 diabetes," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 646-653, 2021.
- [90] O. AlShorman, B. Alshorman, and M. Masadeh, "A Review of Physical Human Activity Recognition Chain Using Sensors," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Informatics (IJEI)*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 560-573, 2020.
- [91] AlShorman, O., Irfan, M., Saad, N., Zhen, D., Haider, N., Glowacz, A. and AlShorman, A., "A Review of Artificial Intelligence Methods for Condition Monitoring and Fault Diagnosis of Rolling Element Bearings for Induction Motor," *Shock and Vibration*, vol. 2020, 2020.